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LETTER FROM DR.EAM - WHO ARE WE?

SAMUEL KIM

Dr.eam Journal began with a singular notion: how can we inspire the next community of health-builders? We want to reimagine medical practice and health education; we seek to inspire the future practitioner to use scientific thinking as a framework for better health systems.

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NETWORK DEDICATED TO
SERVING THE FUTURE BY
SERVING THE FUTURE-
BUILDING LEADERS”**

WHEN OPIOIDS WORSEN PAIN: APPLYING CDC GUIDELINES IN THE ED

MADISON MELTON - EMERGENCY MEDICINE

The CDC's updated opioid prescribing guidelines remind providers to be cautious when managing pain, especially in the emergency department (ED), where opioids are often used for quick relief. One often overlooked complication is opioid-induced hyperalgesia (OIH), a condition where opioids increase a patient's sensitivity to pain. Unlike tolerance, in which patients need higher doses to achieve the same level of relief, OIH can worsen pain when more opioids are given. This distinction is especially important in emergency medicine, where time is limited and accurate clinical judgement both directly impacts patient outcomes and ensures responsible opioid prescribing.

A 2022 cross-sectional study published in the *Clinical Journal of Pain* looked at 150 patients on long-term opioid therapy for chronic pain and found that almost 15% showed signs of OIH. These patients reported higher pain intensity and had lower pain thresholds on exam, even after adjusting for opioid dose and pain diagnosis [1]. The study's findings give real-world evidence to back the CDC's updated guidelines: increasing opioid doses in patients who are not improving may not only be ineffective but also potentially harmful. For emergency physicians, this means thinking twice before increasing the dose when a patient's pain seems disproportionate to the injury or unresponsive to opioids.

The CDC guidelines recommend starting with non-opioid therapies first, like NSAIDs, acetaminophen, or regional nerve blocks. If opioids are used, they should be prescribed at the lowest effective dose for the shortest necessary duration [2]. This will help limit the risk of both opioid misuse and complications like OIH. When OIH is suspected, treatment strategies include opioid tapering or using adjunct medications. Gradual opioid reduction has been shown to improve pain outcomes in OIH patients. Ketamine, an NMDA receptor antagonist, and gabapentin have also shown success in reducing pain sensitivity and improving function in OIH patients [3]. These options are especially valuable in the ED, where quick shifts in treatment plan can prevent unnecessary opioid escalation and reduce adverse symptoms.

Ultimately, recognizing OIH allows emergency clinicians to better tailor their pain management strategies. By applying the CDC's guidelines and staying alert to signs of OIH, ED providers can avoid overtreatments, improve patient outcomes, and contribute to safer opioid prescribing practices.

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ANALYSIS OF “IMAGING OPIOID ANALGESIA IN THE HUMAN BRAIN AND ITS POTENTIAL RELEVANCE FOR UNDERSTANDING OPIOID USE IN CHRONIC PAIN” IN RELATION TO THE 2022 VA/DOD CLINICAL PRACTICE GUIDELINE FOR OPIOID THERAPY FOR CHRONIC PAIN

BRODY WHALEN - RADIOLOGY

Chronic pain management often requires balancing relief with potential risks of opioid treatment. The Department of Veterans Affairs and the Department of Defense (VA/DoD) 2022 guidelines emphasize evidence-based, risk-mitigating decision-making. This paper reviews the neuroimaging article “Imaging Opioid Analgesia in the Human Brain and Its Potential Relevance for Understanding Opioid Use in Chronic Pain,” which explores opioid mechanisms of action in human studies. We compare its insights with the guidelines to assess whether medical imaging findings support or refine clinical recommendations.

The VA/DoD guideline strongly recommends against initiating or continuing long-term opioid therapy for chronic non-cancer pain except in carefully selected cases. It also highlights the importance of patient-centered, shared decision-making, behavioral health screening, risk mitigation strategies such as avoiding benzodiazepine co-prescribing, lowest dose use, regular reevaluation, and consideration of buprenorphine over full agonists due to lower overdose risk. The guideline can be applied beyond just VA/DoD settings, and ultimately emphasizes non-opioid and non-pharmacologic alternatives as preferred first-line interventions in treating chronic pain.

The article “Imaging Opioid Analgesia in the Human Brain and Its Potential Relevance for Understanding Opioid Use in Chronic Pain” reviews neuroimaging evidence on how opioids modulate pain processing in the human brain, offering mechanistic insight into analgesic pathways. It considers MRI and PET findings showing that opioids reduce activity in pain-related cortical and subcortical regions. This reveals that there are brain-level effects that correlate with subjective pain relief. Although it is not a clinical trial, this review bridges basic neuroscience with a clinical phenomenon, showing that analgesia is mediated by measurable brain modulation and suggesting heterogeneity in responses tied to individual neurobiology.

Population: Healthy volunteers or pain-reporting humans undergoing imaging.

Intervention: Administration of opioids (morphine, fentanyl).

Comparison: Placebo or baseline imaging, often with the same subject pre/post opioid comparisons.

Outcome: Neuroimaging markers of pain pathway activity (e.g., decreased Blood Oxygenation Level Dependent/BOLD signal in thalamus) correlate with reported analgesia.

The neuroimaging review does not conflict with this guideline’s recommendations. Rather, it adds mechanistic depth to the guideline’s cautious stance on opioid dependence. While the VA/DoD prioritizes reduced risk due to modest and often transient clinical benefits of opioids, the imaging evidence clarifies why opioid analgesia may vary between patients: brain responses differ across regions and subjects. This supports the guideline’s emphasis on individual risk-benefit assessment, lowest dose use, and regular reevaluation. However, the imaging data does not support the long-term benefit or safety of opioids, which is consistent with guideline warnings. Findings of variable brain responsiveness underscore why non-opioid treatments and personalized approaches align better with neurobiological variability.

In conclusion, this neuroimaging review enhances understanding of opioid analgesia by mapping its effects on the brain, reinforcing the VA/DoD clinical practice guideline's emphasis on individual decision-making and restraint based on variable benefit. While this paper deepens scientific insight, it does not alter the guideline's core recommendations. Staying aware of current research can help refine pain management strategies, even as clinicians adhere to evidence-based guidelines.

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OPIOID PRESCRIBING IN MEDICARE DERMATOLOGY PRACTICES

GRACE DANG - DERMATOLOGY

Opioid prescribing in dermatology has raised growing concerns given the potential for misuse and adverse events, especially in older adults who represent a significant portion of the dermatologic patient population. The 2022 CDC Clinical Practice Guideline for Prescribing Opioids for Pain provides updated recommendations focused on safe opioid use, risk mitigation, and prioritizing nonopioid pain management strategies. This review focuses on opioid use in dermatology, using available data on prescribing patterns and complications to explore how national guidelines apply to clinical practice.

The CDC guideline emphasizes cautious opioid prescribing with individualized risk assessment, favoring nonopioid analgesics and nonpharmacologic therapies when possible. For patients requiring opioids, the guideline recommends using the lowest effective dose, short durations, and frequent monitoring for signs of misuse or any adverse effects. These principles align with dermatology, where procedures often allow for local anesthesia and non-opioid pain management strategies that help reduce the need for opioid prescriptions.

A 2018 cross-sectional study by Cao et al. analyzed Medicare Part D data to characterize opioid prescribing patterns among dermatologists. Of the 12,537 dermatologists evaluated, over 85% either did not prescribe opioids or issued fewer than ten claims in a year. However, a small subset, mainly dermatologists in surgical practices, accounted for a disproportionately higher amount of opioid prescribing. The study also estimated that opioid prescriptions from dermatologists could contribute to long-term opioid use in thousands of beneficiaries, with associated risks such as gastrointestinal and central nervous system side effects, and up to 999 fractures annually. These findings reinforce the importance of aligning dermatologic postoperative care with CDC guidelines by limiting routine opioid use and prioritizing safer alternatives.

In conclusion, this study serves as a critical reminder that even modest prescribing can lead to unintended long-term consequences, particularly in older populations like Medicare recipients. By prioritizing nonopioid options and recognizing patient-specific risks, dermatologists can optimize outcomes and reduce opioid-related complications.

Edited by Shlok Chauhan

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THE USE OF LUBIPROSTONE IN THE TREATMENT OF OPIOID INDUCED CONSTIPATION

WILLIAM HARTMAN - GASTROENTEROLOGY

Opioids are an important group of medications used to treat moderate to severe pain. Despite their efficacy in the treatment of pain, they are known to cause a wide range of adverse effects such as sedation, nausea, dizziness, respiratory depression, and constipation. Constipation is among the most common of these adverse effects, with an estimated prevalence of 40% to 80% in patients taking opioids [2]. The American Gastrointestinal Association (AGA) uses the Rome IV criteria for the diagnosis of opioid induced constipation (OIC), which requires a patient to have recently started or had a dose increase of an opioid and have two or more symptoms of functional constipation [4].

The AGA guidelines use a stepwise addition of medications to treat OIC, starting with traditional laxatives as the first-line agents. These include docusate sodium, polyethylene glycol, mineral oil, and senna. After traditional laxatives, peripherally active μ -Opioid receptor antagonists such as naldemedine, naloxegol, and methylnaltrexone are recommended. As of the most recent AGA guidelines for OIC released in 2019, the AGA makes no recommendation for the use of lubiprostone, citing a lack of evidence [3].

A recent systematic review and meta-analysis from Akram et. al (2025) looked at the use of lubiprostone in the treatment of OIC. The study reviewed 14 randomized controlled trials on lubiprostone from July 2019 to June 2024. Statistical analysis of these 14 studies found an increased rate of spontaneous bowel movements 24 hours after starting lubiprostone in patients with OIC when compared to placebo. Additionally, an increased number of spontaneous bowel movements was found at 8 weeks and 12 weeks with no association with gastrointestinal adverse events [1].

The American Gastrointestinal Association does not currently recommend the use of lubiprostone for the treatment of opioid induced constipation due to a lack of data, with the latest guidelines published in 2019. With new data showing that lubiprostone is effective at producing spontaneous bowel movements in patients with OIC, the AGA may update the guidelines in the future to reflect this data.

Edited by Aarti Palaniappan

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ANALYSIS OF VIRTUAL REALITY- DELIVERED PAIN PSYCHOLOGY THERAPY IN RELATION TO OPIOID USAGE FOR NEUROPATHIC PAIN

TANVI GENTI - NEUROLOGY

The CDC Clinical Practice Guideline for Prescribing Opioids for Pain in November 2022 gives recommendations for how to approach prescribing opioids. It states that physicians should be cautious with prescribing it for chronic pain, and use non-opioid therapies first to treat acute pain conditions like neuropathic pain. The CDC mentions specific medications like serotonin-norepinephrine reuptake inhibitors (SNRIs), NSAIDs, relaxants, antidepressants, and anticonvulsants to treat neuropathic pain or related pain. The CDC also suggested therapies like cognitive-behavioral therapy and physical therapy to include in a pain management plan. The guideline warns against suddenly stopping opioid therapy for the risk of withdrawal or worse pain.

In their 2023 study, Chuan et al. conducted a pilot randomized controlled trial that looked at how impactful a virtual reality (VR)- delivered pain psychology intervention was at alleviating neuropathic pain in cancer patients. There were 39 patients in the study, who were randomly split into a custom VR intervention or a control group that got passive VR content. The VR therapy that the researchers were studying was focused on using VR-guided visualization and continuous muscle-relaxing techniques that reduce pain and eventually the need for opioid usage. The study found that patients in the VR intervention group had a high tolerability and acceptability for the treatment, noting a reduced opioid usage and lower pain severity score in their one and three-month follow-ups. These findings support the potential for VR pain psychology as a viable option to manage neuropathic pain in addition to other treatments.

The findings of Chuan et al. (2023) generally align with the CDC guidelines. Both this study and the guideline talk about the importance of using non-opioid therapies as the first treatment for neuropathic pain. Chuan et al.'s findings that VR interventions are well received by patients and can reduce opioid use and pain impact supports the CDC's emphasis on the benefits of a nonpharmacologic approach. However, while the CDC supports and promotes psychological and behavioral therapies, Chuan et al.'s research shows a new way to apply these interventions clinically and how it could benefit patients, especially cancer patients who might be constantly exposed to opioids to deal with the pain.

In conclusion, the CDC gives a thorough guideline on how to prescribe opioids that puts the patient's safety and wellness first, while mentioning plenty of non-opioid therapies that they can benefit from. Chuan et al. add to this guideline by showing how virtual reality therapies like the VR pain psychology intervention can be another nonpharmacologic tool that can decrease patients' pain and opioid usage. Both the guideline and the study show the importance of looking at new ways to manage pain beyond just medications and reliance on opioids, especially in populations that use them frequently, such as post-op and cancer patients. Ultimately, as VR-based therapies continue to be researched, further studies are needed to confirm how effective they are clinically and how to best integrate them into practice.

Edited by Shlok Chauhan

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Re-Evaluating Opioid Tapering in Cancer Survivors: A Comparison to CDC and NCCN Guidelines

JOEL SETYA - ONCOLOGY

THIS PAPER REVIEWS THE 2022 CDC CLINICAL PRACTICE GUIDELINE FOR PRESCRIBING OPIOIDS AND THE NCCN V2.2025 ADULT CANCER PAIN GUIDELINE BASED ON FINDINGS FROM A LARGE RETROSPECTIVE STUDY BY MAGNAN ET AL. (2023). THE STUDY PROVIDES ESSENTIAL KNOWLEDGE ABOUT OPIOID TAPERING EFFECTS ON REAL-WORLD PATIENTS WHO HAVE CHRONIC PAIN AND ARE OFTEN CANCER SURVIVORS. A REVIEW OF CURRENT TAPERING RECOMMENDATIONS AND THESE RECENT RESULTS HIGHLIGHTS ISSUES WITH APPLYING STANDARDIZED TAPERING POLICIES TO ONCOLOGY SURVIVORSHIP CARE.

To start, the 2022 CDC guideline promotes a personalized care model for opioid tapering because long-term opioid use requires cautious individualized management. The NCCN guideline allows opioid prescription for patients who suffer from chronic cancer-related pain yet it does not establish particular recommendations for cancer survivors. A large number of cancer survivors who require pain management are assigned to general chronic pain pathways by healthcare providers, forcing them to taper their opioids even though their original pain sources remain permanent. The insufficient differentiation in survivorship care produces possible risks for patients who have not recovered from their pain after cancer treatment.

The research by Magnan et al. (2023) evaluated data from 19,000 adult patients who received extended opioid treatment within a United States healthcare system. The study demonstrates that individuals who underwent opioid tapering experienced significantly elevated emergency department visits, hospitalizations, and mental health crisis rates. The observed outcomes remained consistent after researchers applied opioid dosage adjustments, as well as controlled for baseline risk factors and comorbidity variables. The research results indicate a vital problem for survivors who need to control their ongoing treatment-related chronic pain, with the findings indicating that discontinuing opioid therapy causes destabilization in patient care, which results in more frequent emergency service use and worse health outcomes.

The lack of survivorship-specific tapering guidelines creates confusion during medical decision-making. Survivors must deal with pain that stems from nerve damage, fibrosis, and chronic musculoskeletal changes since these conditions remain stable yet incurable. The implementation of tapering protocols on patients with these conditions might decrease their quality of life while generating fresh safety concerns. The growing number of patients requires pain management strategies that are tailored to pain origins and trajectories since current generalized guidelines fail to meet their needs.

Magnan et al. showed that new specific guidelines for tapering are essential according to their study results. Guideline updates should establish clinical decision trees to identify patients with permanent or structural pain conditions who should be exempt from standard tapering procedures. Any opioid tapering plan for cancer survivors should be managed through multidisciplinary teams that include palliative care specialists, mental health professionals, and oncology providers. The recommended strategies would maintain patient safety and appropriate care delivery and meet opioid stewardship goals.

The CDC and NCCN guidelines encourage both cautious and adaptable approaches, yet require additional clarification regarding tapering recommendations for oncology survivors. The concept of survivorship does not automatically indicate the ability to stop opioid use because guidelines should maintain this distinction. The addition of survivorship-focused tapering language in clinical guidelines will support responsible long-term pain management without causing harm to patients.

Edited by Aarti Palaniappan

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ANALYZING POSTOPERATIVE OPIOID STRATEGIES IN RELATION TO THE 2022 CDC OPIOID PRESCRIBING GUIDELINES

REGAN DUNN - SURGERY

The opioid crisis remains a major public health issue, prompting the CDC to issue updated 2022 Clinical Guidelines for opioid prescribing. In this paper, we will review these CDC recommendations, particularly as they relate to acute postoperative pain. We will then analyze a 2021 study by Porter et al., which tested an opioid prescribing protocol for surgical patients. Our goal is to assess how this clinical study aligns with national prescribing guidelines.

The CDC's 2022 Clinical Practice Guideline for Prescribing Opioids for Pain offers evidence-based recommendations for managing acute, subacute, and chronic pain in adults. For acute pain, the guideline highlights that opioid therapy should only be started when the expected benefits outweigh the associated risks of treatment. The guideline recommends non-opioid therapies as the first-line treatment and stresses the importance of using the lowest effective dose of immediate-release opioids when opioids are necessary. Moreover, the guideline states that the duration of opioid usage should generally not exceed three to seven days. Ultimately, the CDC calls for better patient education, shared decision-making, and regular follow-up to reassess pain and risk of harm.

In a 2021 prospective clinical trial, Porter et al. evaluated a patient-centered opioid prescribing protocol developed at Dartmouth-Hitchcock Medical Center. The study involved 229 surgical patients across multiple surgical specialties such as general, colorectal, thoracic, gynecologic, and urologic surgery. Specifically, this study based discharge prescriptions on the patients' in-hospital opioid use on the day prior to discharge. Patients using no opioids received none; those using 1-3 pills received 15 tablets; and those using 4 or more received 30. Moreover, all patients were offered non-opioid analgesics and education on proper opioid disposal. The study found that 93% of patients reported adequate pain control, and 83% safely disposed of unused opioids when given specific instructions and reminders.

Population (P): 229 adult patients undergoing surgery across multiple specialties (hospital stay \geq 48 hours).

Intervention (I): A patient-centered discharge opioid protocol based on opioid use on the day before discharge.

Comparison (C): Comparison to traditional fixed-quantity prescribing methods that often overprescribe opioids irrespective of individual use.

Outcome (O): Primary outcomes included patient satisfaction with pain management (93%) and appropriate disposal of unused opioids (83%).

The findings of Porter et al. (2021) strongly support the principles outlined in the CDC's 2022 opioid prescribing guideline. Both emphasize the importance of tailoring prescriptions to patient-specific needs. The study uniquely applies these principles by basing discharge opioid prescriptions on the previous day's usage, a practice in line with the CDC's recommendation to avoid standard one-size-fits-all prescribing methods. Moreover, the usage of non-opioid analgesics and structured education about proper medication disposal reflects the CDC's guidance to prioritize pain strategies and harm reduction. By demonstrating that most patients can achieve adequate pain control with significantly fewer opioids, Porter et al. provided practical, patient-centered evidence to guide safe opioid prescribing.

In conclusion, the study by Porter et al. provides real-world support for the CDC's 2022 opioid prescribing guidelines. By adjusting prescriptions to in-hospital usage and prioritizing patient education, the protocol reduces unnecessary opioid exposure while maintaining effective pain control. This study highlights how structured, evidence-based approaches can incorporate national recommendations into actionable clinical strategies.

Edited by AJ Jenkins

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ADMINISTRATION OF NALOXONE IN CARDIAC ARREST REGARDLESS OF OPIOID CONSUMPTION HISTORY

MILO COFFEE - CARDIOLOGY

Opioid overdoses are one of the leading causes of death in the United States in injury-related circumstances (Ritter et al., 2022). Whether the overdose is the result of an accident or is intentional, overdoses remain a completely avoidable public health crisis that continues to be fueled by the prescribing of opioids and lack of education around how these drugs work. Two of the major effects of excessive opioids on the body are cardiac muscle toxicity and depression of the respiratory system (Dillon et al., 2024). Both of these can lead to cardiac arrest. This article will evaluate the role of prescribing naloxone to those who have opioid prescriptions and how the inclusion of naloxone in cardiac arrest can change the short term and long term outcomes for these patients.

Current guidelines for the prescription of opioids, compiled by the CDC, dictate when and when not to prescribe opioids. However, the current guidelines also outline the process of prescribing opioids once you have identified an appropriate candidate for opioid therapy. We will focus more on how to prescribe opioids and the implications of starting a patient on opioid therapy. The CDC outlines that once you have identified a patient for opioid therapy, you should also prescribe naloxone (CDC, 2022). Along with the prescription of naloxone, the patient should be educated on what naloxone is, when to use it, and how to use it (CDC, 2022). The prescription of naloxone for the patient is important in preventing accidental overdoses of the patient, but it is also important to prescribe naloxone when there is a member of the household who is identified as a high-risk individual for inappropriate consumption of opioids.

Excessive consumption of opioids can lead to cardiac arrest. So what is the role of opioid reversal in cardiac arrest? All EMS agencies carry naloxone (Narcan) with them when they respond to calls, but what dictates if they give it? Naloxone is given when there is a clear history or signs of opioid consumption, but what if the patient has overdosed on a family member's opioid prescription? What if a patient has received opioids for the first time and they accidentally took too much? In those situations, naloxone administration might not cross the paramedic's mind when they are assessing the unresponsive patient in front of them. A study by Dillon et al examines the difference between out of hospital cardiac arrests (OHCA) where naloxone was administered as part of advanced cardiac life saving (ACLS) and OHCA's where naloxone wasn't administered.

The purpose of the study described above is to evaluate the effectiveness of naloxone administration in out of hospital cardiac arrests. This study was performed retrospectively and identified patients through medical records. It identified 8,195 patients who went into cardiac arrest between 2015-2023. The intervention that was provided was the administration of naloxone in these patients. Out of the total study group, 14.2% received naloxone and of those patients 59.6% of them were not suspected to have opioid induced cardiac arrest (Dillon et al., 2024). Out of the patients that received naloxone, 34.5% of them obtained return of spontaneous circulation (ROSC) while only 22.9% of patients who didn't receive naloxone achieved ROSC (Dillon et al., 2024). This study also looked at long term outcomes of the administration of naloxone during OHCA. It found that of the 34.5% of patients who received naloxone and achieved ROSC, 15.9% of them survived and were discharged from the hospital while only 9.7% of patients who received ROSC after no naloxone administration were discharged (Dillon et al., 2024). This demonstrates a large increase in positive outcomes when naloxone is administered regardless of opioid use history.

While this study is not a direct comparison to the guidelines, it does align well with what the guidelines outline regarding the prescription of naloxone. It also supports the notion that when naloxone is given before arrival to the hospital there is a better chance of achieving ROSC and a higher rate of survivability post-cardiac arrest. It can be difficult to determine if cardiac arrest is due to opioid consumption, especially if the patient is not a known user of opioids. Thus, from a cardiology stance, we would be a proponent of administering naloxone anytime there is an OHCA whether or not there is a history of suspected opioid ingestion. Naloxone when given to someone who is not overdosing on an opioid is harmless thus it can only improve a patient's status after they enter cardiac arrest.

Opioid induced cardiac arrest is a completely preventable death. Whether overdosing on an opioid is the result of accidentally taking too much, taking a pill that is unknowing laced with an opioid, or is a way to intentionally harm oneself, the administration of naloxone can vastly improve the chance of achieving ROSC and increases likelihood of long term survival.

Edited by AJ Jenkins

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WHAT'S NEW WITH DREAM?

This month, we're excited to present our fourth issue! Our writers have done their research on clinical guidelines and recent advancements in their specialties, all through the lens of our monthly theme. We're focusing on anesthesiology this August. Stay tuned for more monthly issues!

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MAGAZINE

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